

Effect of Se-free Annealing on Cesium Fluoride Treated Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Thin Films and Corresponding Solar Cells

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In this work, we investigate the effect of selenium-free annealing on cesium fluoride (CsF) treated Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ (CIGS) thin films and evaluate their solar cell performance. Annealing of CsF-treated CIGS thin films changes the surface morphology, the chemical composition, and reduces the Urbach energies. However, the full benefit of the reduced Urbach energies of the annealed samples is not obtained, because of an increased buffer/CIGS interfacial recombination owing as a consequence of re-evaporation of the alkali-containing layer from the surface region after upon annealing. On the other hand, CsF-treated CIGS thin films without any annealing after the post deposition treatment (PDT) preserves the alkali-containing layer at the surface region, thereby leading to an improved buffer/CIGS interface. Consequently, the open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) and fill factor improve significantly in these devices. The Urbach energies of both annealed and non-annealed solar cells are calculated from external quantum efficiency measurement to understand their impact on V_{OC} and V_{OC} deficit. No correlation between the VOC deficit and the Urbach energies is observed.

1. Introduction

A heavy alkali-metals treatments with potassium (K), rubidium (Rb) and cesium (Cs) on the surface of Cu(In_xGa_{1-x})Se₂ (CIGS) thin -films is an effective route to improve the solar cell performance.^[1-31] This treatment forms an alkali (Alk = K, Rb, Cs) containing indium-selenium (Alk-In-Se) with a larger bandgap on the surface of the CIGS thin film.^[26, 28, 29] The valence band offset at the buffer/CIGS interface increases with the Alk-In-Se layer, which helps to reduce the interface recombination velocity.^[26-29] The thermodynamic stability of these Alk-In-Se layers increases with increasing alkali radius.^[29] Several strategies to intentionally deposit the alkali-related secondary layer on the surface of CIGS thin- films were reported.^[5,11,12,31] Nevertheless, for performance improvement, it is crucial to control the thickness of this secondary layer, as a too thick secondary layer can acts as transport barrier and therefore reduce the fill factor of respective solar cells. ^[30,31]

Cesium-fluoride treated CIGS solar cells, with the absorber layer prepared by a sequential process (selenization/sulfurization of metal precursors) have reached world-record efficiency of 23.35%.^[4] Rb has been suggested for co-evaporated CIGS as an effective element to improve photovoltaic performance.^[3,15] However, these two different CIGS deposition techniques have different reaction pathways for the CIGS formation, influencing also the grain boundary properties, which might have

contributed to this difference in alkali metal.^[32,33] Generally, the alkali-metal post-deposition treatment (PDT) is accompanied by an annealing process with^[1,5,7] and or without^[9,10,16] selenium vapor. However, so far, no detailed studies have been performed on the annealing effect of CIGS thin-films after heavy alkali-metal PDT without selenium vapor. Therefore, this study presents an important approach to reduce material costs during the PDT processes in CIGS thin films without selenium vapor. Additionally, it also provides valuable guidelines for *ex-situ* PDT processes when selenium is challenging to supply.

The Urbach energy (E_U) is an important optical parameter to determine the band tails in semiconductors. Band tails are characterized by a density of states decaying exponentially into the bandgap. Lower E_U indicates fewer tail states in the bandgap, leading to lower defect density, improved carrier mobility, long carrier lifetime, and smaller amplitude of potential fluctuations.^[34-36] We find that annealing CsF-treated CIGS thin films reduces the Urbach energy, which is attributed to the effective diffusion of Cs into the bulk region. However, because of the re-evaporation of the Alk-In-Se layer after annealing, the buffer/CIGS interface recombination increases, which hinders the full improvement of the solar cell's open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) in the solar cell. On the other hand, without annealing after the CsF-PDT, the Urbach energy did not reduce significantly. However, due to the presence of an Alk-In-Se layer at the surface, interface recombination decreased significantly, improving the V_{OC} , fill factor (FF), and solar cell efficiency (η). A CIGS solar cell with an efficiency of 17.2% was obtained without annealing of the CIGS thin-film after the CsF-PDT. In contrast, an efficiency of 15.7% was obtained when annealing the CIGS thin film after the CsF-PDT. The Urbach energies of both types of solar cells (annealed and non-annealed) were calculated from external quantum efficiency to understand its influence on the V_{OC} deficit. No clear correlation of V_{OC} deficit to Urbach energy energy was observed.

2. Result and Discussion

Figure 1. SEM images of (a) CsF-free and CsF-treated CIGS thin films after annealing for (b) 0, (c) 10, and (d) 30 minutes.

Figure 1 shows scanning electronic microscope (SEM) images (without rinsing) of (a) CsF-free and (b)-(d) CsF-treated CIGS thin films for annealing periods of 0, 10, and 30 minutes, respectively, which are represented as $\text{CsF}_{0\text{min-ann}}$, $\text{CsF}_{10\text{min-ann}}$, and $\text{CsF}_{30\text{min-ann}}$ throughout the paper. The substrate temperature during the annealing process was 350 °C. The post-deposition treatment and annealing conditions are described in the experimental section below. As shown in Figure 1(b), CsF-treatment without additional annealing ($\text{CsF}_{0\text{min-ann}}$) formed bright (represented by arrows) regions around grain boundaries on the surface of CIGS thin film. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) energy dispersive X-ray diffraction (EDX) mapping confirmed that the bright regions were Cs-containing compounds.^[18, 22] After 10 minutes of annealing ($\text{CsF}_{10\text{min-ann}}$) [Figure 1(c)], the bright regions on the CIGS surface were reduced. Further annealing of the sample up to 30 minutes ($\text{CsF}_{30\text{min-ann}}$) [Figure 1(d)] generated rough surfaces and canal-like structures around the grain boundaries, which is attributed to the re-evaporation of Cs-related compounds (Cs-In-Se) as well as

diffusion of Cs into the grain boundaries.

To justify this statement, cross-sectional SEM images of $\text{CsF}_{0\text{min-ann}}$ [Figure 2 (a and c)] and $\text{CsF}_{30\text{min-ann}}$ [Figure 2 (b and d)] were examined after deionized (DI) water and HCl rinsing (the HCl solution was prepared with a ratio of 1: 10 in DI water). It is well known that HCl solution effectively etched Alk-In-Se compounds from the surface of CIGS thin films, whereas water cannot etch the Alk-In-Se compounds. [1,28] This means, the presence of Alk-In-Se layer in the surface of the CIGS thin film can also be characterized by rinsing the sample in HCl solution.

In Figure 2 (a) ($\text{CsF}_{0\text{min-ann}}$ thin film), a large grain of Cs-In-Se compound remained between the CIGS grains even after DI water rinsing, which was successfully removed by HCl rinsing [Figure 2 (c), shown by arrow]. In contrast to this, for $\text{CsF}_{30\text{min-ann}}$ thin films [Figure 2 (b)], such large Cs-In-Se grains were not observed. However, smaller Cs-In-Se grains were observed deeper into the grain boundaries, but were successfully removed by the HCl solution [Figure 2 (d), shown by arrow]. It is expected that the absence of large grains of Alk-In-Se at the surface of the $\text{CsF}_{30\text{min-ann}}$ thin film is due to the re-evaporation of Alk-In-Se from the surface of the CIGS thin film. The vapor pressures of Cs, Se, and In are in the order of $\text{Cs} > \text{Se} > \text{In}$. [37] Additionally, annealing also diffused Alk-In-Se compounds into the grain boundaries.

Figure 2. Cross-sectional SEM images of (a,c) CsF_{0min-ann} and (b,d) CsF_{30min-ann} CIGS thin films after water and HCl rinsing.

Figure 3 shows the basic solar cell parameters, open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), short-circuit current density (J_{sc}), fill factor (FF), and efficiency (η) of Al/Ni/ZnO:Al/ZnO/CBD-CdS/CIGS/Mo/SLG solar cells (without anti-reflective (AR) coating) fabricated from CsF-free and CsF-treated CIGS absorber layers (CsF_{0min-ann}, CsF_{10min-ann}, and CsF_{30min-ann}). It can be noticed that V_{oc} , FF , and η improved significantly for the CsF-treated CIGS solar cells and show maximum values for the CsF_{0min-ann} absorber.

Figure 3. The basic solar cell parameters of CsF-free and CsF-treated CIGS solar cells (CsF_{0min-ann}, CsF_{10min-ann}, and CsF_{30min-ann}) without AR coating.

The J - V and EQE curves of the best solar cells are shown in Figure 4. The solar cells fabricated using CsF-free, CsF_{0min-ann}, CsF_{10min-ann}, and CsF_{30min-ann} absorber layers have η of 14.5%, 17.2 %, 16.0%, and 15.5% respectively.

16.0 %, and 15.7 %, respectively. The detailed photovoltaic parameters are given in Table 1. Diode parameters of the J-V curves [Table 1] were extracted using the one-diode equation model under illumination. [38]

$$J = J_{ph} - J_0 \left(e^{\frac{q(V+R_s J)}{nKT}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V+R_s J}{R_{sh}} \quad , \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

where ‘J’ is the current density, ‘V’ is the applied voltage, J_{ph} is the photocurrent, ‘ J_0 ’ is the reverse saturation current, ‘n’ is the ideality factor of the diode, ‘K’ is the Boltzmann constant, ‘T’ is the absolute temperature, and ‘ R_s ’ and ‘ R_{sh} ’ are the series and shunt resistance of the diode, respectively.

Figure 4. Typical (a) J-V characteristics and (b) EQE spectra of CsF-free and CsF-treated CIGS solar cells (CsF_{0min-ann}, CsF_{10min-ann}, and CsF_{30min-ann}) without AR coating. The bandgap of the CIGS solar cell was estimated from the first EQE derivative (dEQE/dλ), where λ represents the wavelength.

The J_0 and n of CsF_{0min-ann} solar cell were found to be lower than those of the other solar cells. The reason for this will be discussed later based on the analysis of surface properties at the buffer/CIGS interface using TEM/EDX line scans and temperature-dependent current-voltage measurements (J-V-T).

The J-V curve of the CsF_{30min-ann} solar cell is not increasing in the similar manner to the CsF_{0min-ann} and CsF_{10min-ann} solar cells and have crosses the J-V curve of the CsF_{0min-ann} solar cell at a forward bias voltage above V_{OC} , which is attributed to a barrier-like behavior. In our previous experiments,

we noticed that annealing of CsF-treated CIGS solar cells forms a back-contact barrier indicated by J-V rollover. [27] Hence, the CsF_{0min-ann} solar cell forms a better potential barrier across the CIGS/Mo interfaces, leading to a larger FF as compared to the CsF_{30min-ann} solar cell.

Table 1. Cell parameters (without AR coating) and V_{OC} deficits of CIGS solar cells shown in Figure 3 (a).

	J_{SC} (mA/cm ²)	V_{OC} (mV)	FF	Eff (%)	R_s (Ω .cm ⁻²)	R_{sh} (Ω .cm ⁻²)	J_0 (A/cm ²)	n	$(E_g/q)-V_{OC}$ (V)	E_U (meV)
CsF-free	34.2	602	0.702	14.5	0.491	2662	9.01×10^{-4}	2.21	0.528	19.3
CsF _{0min-ann}	34.4	672	0.743	17.2	0.474	3694	7.63×10^{-7}	1.47	0.458	18.2
CsF _{10min-ann}	34.9	652	0.704	16.0	0.504	2728	6.83×10^{-6}	1.63	0.478	18.9
CsF _{30min-ann}	34.0	659	0.700	15.7	0.630	2508	4.57×10^{-6}	1.65	0.471	17.4

The EQE curves of the solar cells are shown in Figure 4(b). The CsF_{0min-ann} solar cell shows a similar EQE curves to the CsF-free CIGS solar cell, except at the shorter wavelength region (400-520 nm), which is due to the thinner CdS layer in the CsF_{0min-ann} solar cell with a slightly improved J_{SC}. Similarly, the CsF_{10min-ann} solar cell shows improved carrier collection in the shorter and longer wavelength regions leading to the highest J_{SC} value. However, the CsF_{30min-ann} solar cells show poor carrier collection in the longer wavelength range (820 nm to 1030 nm). It is expected that the annealing of the CsF_{30min-ann} absorber layer does not only re-evaporate Cs-compounds from the surface [Figure 1d] but also diffuses some portion of Cs deeper into the bulk region towards the Mo back contact, where it replaces Na ions. [10] The rear surface of the CIGS layer contains a Cu-poor region, which tends to accommodate alkali metals that passivate mono-vacancy (V_{Cu}), di-vacancies ($V_{Cu}-V_{Se}$), and vacancy clusters. [39] Na, because of its smaller atomic radius, diffuses easily from the soda-lime glass substrate into these vacancies during the growth of CIGS and passivates such point defects. [39-42] When an excess of Na ions gets exchanged with heavy-alkali metals, the residual defects in the bulk regions previously passivated by Na, become active and may act as recombination centers in the quasi-neutral bulk region reducing J_{SC}. [39, 43] This can be one of the reasons for having slightly lower J_{SC} in the CsF_{30min-ann} solar cells.

A bandgap of 1.13 eV was calculated from the first EQE derivative. The exponential tail at the long-wavelength edge of the EQE above E_g has been used to calculate the Urbach energy (E_U).^[5, 23, 34-36] The comparison of the E_U values estimated from internal and external quantum efficiency at the long-wavelength edge show similar results.^[36] Therefore, E_U values have been calculated from EQE curves of CsF-free and CsF-treated (CsF_{0min-ann}, CsF_{10min-ann}, CsF_{30min-ann}) CIGS solar cells using Eq. (2).^[36,44]

$$\ln(\text{EQE}) = C + \frac{h\nu}{E_U} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where C and $h\nu$ are a constant and photon energy, respectively. The linear region below the E_g of CIGS is related to Urbach absorption and is used to extract the E_U .^[5, 34-36] For the high accuracy of the E_U values, the correlation coefficient of experimental data and fitted line is closer to unity.

Figure 5. Typical $\ln(\text{EQE})$ vs. photon energy curves of CsF-free and CsF-treated CIGS solar cells (CsF_{0min-ann}, CsF_{10min-ann}, and CsF_{30min-ann}) in at the long-wavelength edge.

Figure 5 displays $\ln(\text{EQE})$ vs. $h\nu$ curves of the solar cells. The calculated E_U of CsF-free, CsF_{0min-ann}, CsF_{10min-ann}, and CsF_{30min-ann} solar cells were 19.3, 18.2, 18.9 and 17.4 meV, respectively. Similar to previous results^[23, 36], the E_U of the CsF-treated CIGS solar cells are lower when compared to the CsF-free solar cell. The reduced E_U is explained by heavy alkali-metals at the grain boundaries

removing charged defects and reducing the band bending at grain boundaries. [26] Additionally, it has been suggested that Cs_{Cu} , which is more favourable to form among the Cs-related point defects, annihilates the deep gap states at grain boundaries. Na_{Cu} , on the other hand, is not that much effective to remove these gap states at the grain boundaries [45, 46] and Cs passivates the grain boundaries more effectively than Na. [45]

Urbach tails are likely to be related to a variation in the bond lengths, band gap fluctuations and electrostatic potential fluctuations. [34 and therein] Electrostatic potential fluctuations arise from local inhomogeneities of charged defects. [47] The suppression of charged defects and effective passivation of grain boundaries in CsF-treated CIGS thin films lower the electrostatic potential fluctuations that help to reduce tail states, and thus the E_U . Although a lower E_U was observed for CsF-treated CIGS solar cells as compared to CsF-free CIGS solar cells, a clear correlation between V_{OC} (and V_{OC} deficit) to E_U was not observed among the samples ($CsF_{0min-ann}$, $CsF_{10min-ann}$, and $CsF_{30min-ann}$). For example, the samples with $CsF_{30min-ann}$ that exhibit low values of E_U suffer from larger V_{OC} deficits. This result is consistent with the report presented by EMPA where a clear correlation between E_U and the V_{OC} deficit was not observed for CIGS solar cells with various CGI ratios. [5] These results indicate that the V_{OC} deficit in the solar cell does not always correlate with the lower value of E_U but gets influenced by other factors. We believe that annealing the sample effectively diffuses Cs into the bulk region for our $CsF_{30min-ann}$ CIGS solar cells. However, the same annealing process removed the Cu-poor layer (alkali metal-containing layer) from the surface region, thus increasing recombination at the CdS/CIGS interface. This is one of the main reasons for the lack of correlation between the E_U value and the V_{OC} deficit for the $CsF_{30min-ann}$ CIGS solar cells.

Figure 6. TEM image of the CdS/CIGS interface (top), and the corresponding EDX line profiles (bottom) of (a) CsF_{0min-ann} and (b) CsF_{30min-ann} solar cells.

Aiming at a deeper understanding, we performed TEM on CsF_{0min-ann} and CsF_{30min-ann} solar cells in the vicinity of the CdS/CIGS interface to analyze the effect of the annealing on the CIGS surface and the improvement of the buffer/CIGS interface. The blue dots in the TEM image [top part of Figure 6 (a) and (b)] indicate the scanning path of the electron beam. The elemental depth profiles bottom part of Figure 6 (a) and (b) show a decreased concentration of selenium and indium for CsF_{30min-ann} solar cell compared to the CsF_{0min-ann} sample after annealing. This indicates the removal of the Cu-poor region (Alk-In-Se) from the surface of the CsF_{30min-ann} absorber layer by annealing, verifying the assumption mentioned above. The corresponding CGI and GGI ratio near the CdS/CIGS interface obtained from Figure 6 (a) and (b) is given in Figure 7. Due to the reduction of In and Se in the surface region of the annealed sample (CsF_{30min-ann}), the CGI and GGI ratio near the interface increased. Hence, the reduced Cu-poor region at the CIGS surface and grain boundaries in the CsF_{30min-ann} absorber layer did not form a better p-n junction during the CBD-CdS process compared to the CsF_{0min-ann} sample. Therefore, a slightly degraded CdS/CIGS junction formation in CsF_{30min-ann} solar cell increases the reverse saturation current in the device as observed in Table 1.

Figure 7. CGI and GGI ratio of $\text{CsF}_{0\text{min-ann}}$ (dotted lines) and $\text{CsF}_{30\text{min-ann}}$ (solid lines) solar cells calculated from Figure 6.

J - V - T measurements were performed to analyze the recombination pathway at the CdS/CIGS interface for $\text{CsF}_{0\text{min-ann}}$ and $\text{CsF}_{30\text{min-ann}}$ solar cells. For comparison analysis, J - V - T was also performed for the CsF-free CIGS solar cell. From the linear extension of $V_{OC}(T)$ to $T = 0$ K, the activation energy can be obtained. A higher value of the activation energy usually indicates lower interface recombination.^[48] The V_{OC} at $T = 0$ K for the $\text{CsF}_{0\text{min-ann}}$ solar cell (1.21 eV) is higher than that of the CsF-free (1.07 eV) and the $\text{CsF}_{30\text{min-ann}}$ (1.19 eV) solar cells (Figure 8), indicating the formation of a better buffer/CIGS interface in the $\text{CsF}_{0\text{min-ann}}$ solar cell in line with the observed lower value of J_0 and n in Table 1. The poor interface quality in the $\text{CsF}_{30\text{min-ann}}$ solar cell as compared to the $\text{CsF}_{0\text{min-ann}}$ solar cell leads to higher interface recombination. Interface recombination controls the quasi Fermi level splitting of the solar cell and limits the V_{OC} even with the higher quasi Fermi level splitting of the absorber. ^[49, 50]

For the CsF-treated CIGS solar cells ($\text{CsF}_{0\text{min-ann}}$ and $\text{CsF}_{30\text{min-ann}}$), we observed the extrapolated V_{OC} (at $T = 0$ K) to be larger than the bandgap derived from the first order derivative of the EQE curves $[d(\text{EQE}) / d\lambda]$. Similar inconsistencies were observed previously for KF ^[51, 52] and CsF-treated

[53, 54] CIGS solar cells. The authors then used the *average* E_g value to analyze the recombination mechanisms. [51-54] Here, the calculated *average* E_g was obtained as 1.21 eV, based on the equation $E_g(x) = 1.018 + 0.575x + 0.108x^2$, [55] where x is the GGI ratio. For the $\text{CsF}_{0\text{min-ann}}$ solar cell, the V_{OC} at $T = 0\text{K}$ was equivalent to the *average* E_g , which is characteristic for high-efficiency CIGS solar cells.[14]

Figure 8. Temperature dependence of open-circuit voltage of (a) CsF-free (black line) and CsF-treated CIGS solar cells after annealing for 0 (blue line) and 30 (red line) minutes.

3. Conclusion

The effect of annealing on CsF-PDT CIGS thin-films at a temperature of 350 °C during 0, 10, and 30 minutes without supplying selenium vapor was investigated. SEM images show bright regions on the surface of CIGS thin films after CsF-PDT. When annealing time was increased, the Cu-poor layer from the surface region re-evaporates. As a result, CdS/CIGS interface recombination increased in the annealed samples ($\text{CsF}_{10\text{min-ann}}$ and $\text{CsF}_{30\text{min-ann}}$ solar cells) reducing the V_{OC} . Due to the diffusion of Cs into the bulk region upon annealing of the $\text{CsF}_{30\text{min-ann}}$ sample, two different effects were confirmed from EQE measurements: (i) Poor carrier collection in the longer wavelengths region (820 nm to 1030 nm), which was attributed to the replacement of excess Na ions with Cs ions that activate

residual defects in the bulk region, and (ii) reduction of potential fluctuations as observed by reduced Urbach energies. The former detrimental result is related to the Na effect, whereas the latter beneficial result is related to a Cs effect on the bulk region. However, it was found that the V_{OC} deficit in CsF_{30min-ann} solar cell does not correlate with the Urbach energy, as many factors (here surface properties) influence the V_{OC} deficit. On the other hand, the TEM/EDX depth profile showed a higher concentration of indium and selenium at the surface region of the CsF_{0min-ann} absorber layer, which helps to form a better potential barrier across the buffer/CIGS interface, thereby improving the V_{OC} and FF. These findings provide valuable guidelines for *ex-situ* PDT processes where supplying selenium during the CsF-treatment is challenging, and a way to efficiently reduce the production cost solar cells.

4. Experimental Section

CIGS thin films were deposited on molybdenum (Mo)-coated soda-lime glass (SLG) substrates (30 mm × 30 mm × 1.8 mm) via a three-stage co-evaporation process. An approximately 3 μm thick CIGS thin film was prepared at a substrate temperature of around 530 °C following previously published deposition conditions.^[12] After the CIGS deposition, CIGS/Mo/SLG substrates were taken out of the chamber and divided into four groups. Three groups were treated with CsF-PDT under identical conditions at a substrate temperature of 350 °C for 2 minutes. The source temperature of the CsF containing Knudsen-cell was 430 °C. The only variation performed in these three sets of samples was the annealing time after the CsF-deposition. The substrate temperature during the annealing process was 350 °C. The annealing times were 0, 10, and 30 minutes, and samples are represented as CsF_{0min-ann}, CsF_{10min-ann}, and CsF_{30min-ann} throughout the manuscript. No selenium (Se) was supplied during the CsF-treatment and annealing periods. The fourth group of the CIGS/Mo/SLG substrates was kept without CsF-treatment for comparative analysis (CsF-free). Many sets of experiments were repeated with the conditions mentioned above to check the reproducibility of the work. In all the experiments, similar results were obtained.

Before fabricating the solar cells, the CsF-treated CIGS thin films were rinsed in distilled water for around 10 minutes to remove water-soluble impurities. Then, a cadmium sulfide (CdS) buffer layer was deposited by a chemical-bath deposition (CBD) method. Here, a cadmium sulfate (0.015 M,

CdSO₄) and a thiourea (1.5 M, CH₄N₂S) in ammonia (2.2 M, NH₃) solution was used at the bath temperature of 65 °C during 9 minutes. The CdS buffer layer deposition was performed separately for the CsF-free CIGS/Mo/SLG substrates to eliminate Cs contamination during the CBD process.

A sputtered non-doped high-resistivity ZnO layer was used as a second buffer layer. Subsequently, a low resistivity ZnO:Al (2 wt% Al₂O₃-doped ZnO) window layer was sputtered. Finally, an Al/Ni grid pattern was evaporated as an electrode to complete the solar cell structure. The device area of the solar cell was measured using a digital microscope (VH-6300, Keyence, Japan). Current-voltage (J-V) characterization of the solar cells was performed under A.M 1.5, 100 mW/cm² illumination at 25 °C. A silicon standard cell was used to calibrate the solar simulator (Class A for spectrum match, YSS-80, Yamashita Denso Corporation). The average film composition of the CIGS absorbers was measured using an inductively-coupled plasma spectrometer (SPS7700, Hitachi High-Tech Science). The average chemical composition ratios of the CIGS thin films were determined to be around [Cu]/([In]+[Ga]) (CGI) = 0.91 and [Ga]/([Ga]+[In]) (GGI) = 0.32. The CIGS properties were characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (field emission scanning electron microscope [FESEM] S4800, Hitachi) and transmission electron microscopy with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (TEM-EDX) (JEOL JEM-2100F). The TEM lamellae were prepared using a focused ion beam (FIB) with a thickness of approximately 100 nm. The compositional analysis was carried out using energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) in the vicinity of CdS/CIGS interface.

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